

Steel bridge rehabilitation strategies in Western Canada

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ABSTRACT

Many steel bridges in Western Canada were built in the 1950s to 1970s. Now they exhibit signs of significant deterioration and are in need of rehabilitation or retrofit. Typical deterioration mechanisms include coating failure, corrosion of steel girders with section loss, and fatigue cracking. Furthermore, functional demands on these structures have increased over time resulting in the need for structural intervention to widen the roadway cross sections and accommodate heavier live loads. This paper discusses typical rehabilitation strategies and strengthening methods for aging steel bridges through three case studies from recent and ongoing projects. The case studies illustrate strengthening approaches for shear and flexural capacity, design and field requirements for recoating to achieve enhanced durability and service life extension, and addressing the presence of fatigue cracks. Strengthening methods include installation of bolted flange plates, adding shear connectors to make bridge decks composite with the supporting girders, installing stiffeners and web plate panels. Projects with coating failure have challenges with predicting the amount of corrosion loss and required repairs.

Keywords: steel bridges, rehabilitation, retrofit, strengthening

1 INTRODUCTION

A large number of Canadian highway bridges have been built since the 1950s, which was the era when many of Western Canada's major highways were then either built or relocated to improved alignments. Many bridges built between 1950 and 1970 are steel or concrete bridges. Typically steel bridges of the era are deck-on-girder or truss bridges. Many of these structures have been in need of renewal and have required intervention to varying degrees. Except near large urban centres, two-lane highways have often been appropriate for current and expected future traffic volumes in Western Canada. Hence, renewal often needs to address upgrades to shoulder width and barriers without having to add traffic lanes. Rehabilitation, strengthening, and improvement of existing structures to extend their service lives is a sustainable way of maintaining our infrastructure and generally more desirable than replacement. This paper examines the renewal of aging steel highway bridges in three case studies, concentrating on steel-specific issues. The case studies demonstrate how typical renewal items can be addressed including strengthening of existing girder bridges to upgrade functionality, address coating and cross-section loss due to corrosion, and address fatigue cracks and fracture-prone details.

2 CASE STUDY I – STRENGTHENING OF BRIDGE GIRDERS

The first case study shows how targeted strengthening of a structure allowed to widen the deck and improve safety and functionality. The 481 m long Alexandra Bridge (*Fig. 1*) is located on Trans-Canada Highway 1 in the Fraser Canyon of British Columbia (BC), Canada. Highway 1 is one of the

most important transportation routes between the West Coast and the remainder of Canada. The structure, built in the early 1960's, crosses the Fraser River via a 257 m riveted steel arch main span and has multiple steel girder approach spans. The bridge also crosses a Canadian Pacific Kansas City Railway track under the west approach spans and a Canadian National Railway track under the east approach spans. The two-lane concrete deck was non-composite with the steel structure below. Abutments and piers are made of reinforced concrete. This case study focuses on the strengthening of the approach spans, which was part of a larger rehabilitation project. More details on the general rehabilitation project can be found in (1).

Fig. 1: Plan and Elevation Views of the Alexandra Bridge (adapted from 1)

The approach spans consist of two distinct systems (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2):

- System 1 between the West Abutment and Pier 1 comprises exterior girders and four stringer lines with full height floor beams and a concrete deck. The two intermediate supports (Columns 1 and 2) carry the exterior girders on either side of the railway track and are staggered. The irregularity of the spans requires two counterweights, one at the west abutment, and the other at the diagonally opposite corner at Pier 1 to counteract uplift at these locations.
- System 2 between Piers 1 and 4 and between Piers 5 and the East Abutment consists of continuous three-span systems with four continuous girder lines and a concrete deck with diaphragms and intermediate bracing.

Fig. 2: Alexandra Bridge: a) System 1, b) End Span of System 2 with System 1 in Background

One of the key features of the renewal was to widen the deck and upgrade the bridge barriers to current standards as shown in Fig. 3. The sidewalks and railings of the existing deck did not meet current standards, were a traffic hazard, and were heavily deteriorated. In addition, the original lanes had virtually no shoulders. The new cross section allowed for regular-width traffic lanes and shoulders as well as barriers meeting current Canadian standards. Note that the bridge is in a rural area with very limited pedestrian traffic, hence a sidewalk was not needed.

Fig. 3: Bridge Deck Section Before and After Rehabilitation (1)

A load evaluation of the structure showed that only the exterior girders required upgrading because the exterior girders had lower moment and shear resistance in the original design than the interior girders, which carried most of the live load. With the deck widening and removal of the sidewalk, the following strengthening was required for the exterior girders to have adequate load carrying capacity under the Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code (2):

1. *Moment strengthening by making the exterior girders composite with the deck:* As shown in Fig. 3, the deck widening included removal of the sidewalk and railing which provided access to the top flanges of the exterior girders. This allowed the installation of new shear studs using the regular stud welding process (Fig. 4a). Despite the age of the bridge, the shear studs were designed not only for the ultimate limit state but also for a fatigue limit state meeting the requirements for new design. This was done because future inspection of the studs would be impossible. Making the deck composite with the exterior girders alleviated the majority of the strengthening needs with only required additional localized strengthening requirements remaining as described in the following points.
2. *Moment strengthening in the positive moment region of System 1 by adding cover plates to the bottom flange:* The existing girders had rivetted cover plates in the positive and negative moment zones. These plates needed to be extended in the longer exterior girder spans of

System 1. This was achieved by bolting new cover plates to the bottom flange and splicing the new and old plates with bolted splice plates.

3. *Combined moment and shear interaction strengthening by adding web plates at the columns in System 1:* The negative moment regions over the Columns 1 and 2 provided the biggest challenge for the strengthening, since the moment-shear interaction resistance was inadequate. Adding transverse or longitudinal stiffeners would not have provided adequate capacity. In addition, adding moment resistance would also have been challenging due to the existing cover plates and stiffeners. Hence, it was decided to install web plates in the three web fields over each column (Fig. 4b). The plates were bolted to the web and welded to the transverse stiffeners and welded to the transverse stiffeners at each side and the bottom flange angles. In the tension zone at the top, a bolted splice was used to connect the web plates to the top flange angles. This was done to avoid unfavourable fatigue details (i.e. details with low detail category numbers). Given the size of the web panels, the weight of the new plates was limited so that installation was feasible without large equipment.
4. *Shear strengthening by adding transverse stiffeners near the end supports of System 2 (west approach only):* These additional stiffeners were located at 500 mm from the centreline of the bearing and were also used as new jacking stiffeners for bearing replacement.
5. *Buckling prevention near the intermediate supports of System 2 (west approach only) by adding a longitudinal stiffener (Fig. 4c):* Longitudinal stiffeners were added in two web fields near Piers 2 and 3 to prevent buckling of the slender girder web in bending.

Fig. 4: a) Shear Stud Installation at Top of Exterior Girders, b) Installation of Web Plates (Prior to Deck Widening), and c) Installation of Longitudinal Stiffeners

Other renewal items included counterweight enhancement, bearing replacement, replacement of the deck drainage system, and relocation of historic bridge elements.

All work items were designed to be carried out while maintaining a minimum of single lane traffic on the structure, since there is no reasonable detour available at this location. The strengthening of the girders did not require large equipment, was easy to install and was a cost-effective way of widening the structure and allowing for functionality and roadside safety upgrades to maintain the structure for many years to come.

3 CASE STUDY II – RECOATING AND REPAIR OF SECTION LOSS

Prior to the availability of weathering steel, bridges in Western Canada were typically coated with a lead-based paint system. Depending on the climate and location of the structures, these paint systems have proven to be fairly efficient. However, coating systems have deteriorate over time, eventually leading to coating failure and corrosion and section loss. In order to enhance the service life of the coating, regular inspections and touch-up painting would be required. Once the coating has

deteriorated over large areas, it is typical to recoat the structure by fully removing the existing coating system to bare metal and apply a new coating system. Typical recoating systems in Canada are three coat systems consisting of an organic zinc rich primer, an epoxy intermediate coat, and a polyurethane topcoat. Recoating is a complex and costly process, since the lead removal requires elaborate containments, the surface preparation of the steel to bare metal, which is required for the new coating system to obtain its service life, is cumbersome, and the new application of the new coating requires maintaining appropriate environmental condition.

Using again the Alexandra Bridge from case study I as example, case study II shows the effects of coating failure in the floor system of the arch span and how coating and cross-section loss were addressed. The floor system consists of full-depth floor beams and exterior girders framing into the arch columns (*Fig. 1* and *Fig. 5a*). Four stringer lines frame into the floor beams.

During the original inspection with a snooper truck (underbridge inspection truck) in 2012, several locations of the arch floor system were inspected visually at close proximity. While some coating failure and corrosion was observed in the arch span floor system (*Fig. 5b*), the extent did not require the design of steel repairs at that time. Once scaffolding was installed and access to the floor system available during the 2017/18 rehabilitation works, the deterioration had progressed significantly, and major section loss was observed in portions of the floor system. The deterioration was concentrated below deck breather joints at each floor beam and had progressed at several locations to perforations of floor beam webs, floor beam stiffeners, and stringer ends.

Fig. 5: a) General Overview of Arch Floor System Showing Exterior Girders, Stringers, and Floor Beams, b) Extent of Deterioration during 2012 Inspection at a Typical Floor Beam

Fig. 6: Section Loss due to Corrosion: a) Stringer, b) Floor Beam at Stringer, and c) Floor Beam Web and Stiffener

The observed deterioration initiated a systematic and detailed assessment of the arch span floor system which required cleaning of the steel to determine section loss. Based on field information, the extent of the section loss at all locations was quantified, and repairs were developed in short order. The required number of repairs was extensive, and the owner decided to postpone the repairs to a separate contract in 2019. Hence, only recoating of the deteriorated areas was carried out in the 2017/18 contract. The deferral of the repairs was a funding-based decision and presented some risk. This risk was deemed acceptable by the owner, since the 2017/18 rehabilitation eliminated all breather joints and had all deteriorated members recoated, thus, it was unlikely that further section loss occurred, until the repairs were completed.

Fig. 7: a) Retrofit of Stringer and Floor Beam Deterioration, b) Floor Beam at Column Section Loss, and c) Retrofit of Floor Beam at Column

The deferral of the repairs until 2019 gave time for a detailed load rating of the floor system to assess load capacity of the deteriorated floor system and target inspections to locations where strengthening was actually required. The repairs primarily used bolting and coring and minimized the use of field welding and touch-up coating. Since the repairs were carried out after completion of the coating, they were designed under the assumption of zero slip resistance between members. The repair plates consisted of galvanized plates, which did not receive a coloured topcoat, since they are not visible to the public. Epoxy bedding was applied between existing structures and new plates to fill any gaps and irregularities to avoid moisture build-up and premature deterioration in the future.

The following shows several typical repairs in the floor system:

1. *Deterioration at stringer ends:* Significant section loss was observed at the bottom of the stringer web and bottom flange as well as the clip angles between the floor beams and stringers, see Fig. 6a. The deterioration was mostly limited to the stringer ends where the moment demands are relatively low but the shear demands are high. Therefore, it was sufficient to install web strengthening plates on the stringers and replace heavily deteriorated clip angles (Fig. 7a). In addition, weld material was placed to fill the gap between the stringers and floor beam seats to assure adequate force transfer from the strengthening plate to the stringer flange by bearing.
2. *Deterioration in floor beams at stringers:* Heavy section loss with perforations also occurred in the floor beam webs at the stringer locations, see Fig. 6b. Since access for repairs at this location was difficult, it was chosen to carry out indirect strengthening and repair. In order to assure adequate force flow, additional stiffeners were attached to the floor beam at both sides of the stringer (Fig. 7a). Perforations and section loss in the floor beam web were ground smooth, and relief holes were cored at the edges of the perforations/section loss to minimize the risk for fatigue crack formation in the future (Fig. 7a).
3. *Deterioration in Floor beam webs:* Pitting corrosion occurred at the bottom of the floor beam webs and at the bottom of floor beam stiffeners (Fig. 6c). Where the deterioration of the web

was long and deep enough to impact the shear force flow through the floor beam, web plates were installed (*Fig. 7a*). Where several stiffeners in a row showed severe corrosion at the bottom, every second stiffener was strengthened. This approach was validated by the load rating results.

4. *Deterioration of floor beam webs at arch columns:* Perforations also occurred at the bottom of the floor beam webs at the arch columns (*Fig. 7b*). These locations were strengthened by bolting welded L-shaped sections to the existing structure (*Fig. 7c*). Existing bolts and rivets were replaced with new bolts, and new bolts were added as needed. A filler plate was required over half the girder flange width to achieve even bearing.

Carrying out the repairs in a separate contract had the advantage of better planning and repair optimization as well as better use of trades and labour on site. On the other hand, the second contract required that access be installed a second time and left the structure in a more vulnerable condition for another 18 months. In summary, the targeted repairs of the steel corrosion brought up the floor system capacity to satisfy current Canadian code loading requirements. The case study also shows the extent and fast progression of corrosion when chloride-laden water has access to bare steel. Owners should consider prioritizing investment in coating operations to minimize costly steel repairs.

4 CASE STUDY III – REPAIR AND RETROFIT OF FATIGUE AND FRACTURE-PRONE DETAILS

Fatigue cracking is a common deterioration mechanism in ageing steel bridges. In addition, certain details can lead to unannounced, brittle fracture in the member. Fatigue and fracture-prone details are often found in older steel bridges which were before current knowledge of fatigue and fracture mechanisms became available. This case study shows renewal of fatigue details and cracks as well as retrofit to details where potential brittle failure can occur. The fracture type discussed in this case study is called “constraint-induced fracture” (CIF) (3). There are typically three conditions which must all be present for a detail to be susceptible to CIF: a) A stress concentration due to a crack-like geometric configuration that is subjected to applied stress; b) high residual tensile stresses and; c) through thickness constraint (triaxial stress condition) (3). Since it is impossible to predict residual stresses and the likelihood of failure in CIF critical details, the only effective retrofit is to eliminate conditions leading to CIF.

Fig. 8: Waskatenau Bridge over the North Saskatchewan River in Alberta – Typical Multi-Span Two Girder Line Bridge with Fatigue and CIF Susceptible Details (4)

There are several welded steel girder bridges built in Alberta since the 1960s, which have shown fatigue cracking as well as CIF susceptible details. In particular, two girder line systems with their limited redundancy were determined as high-risk by the Owner and renewal was carried out. *Fig. 8*

shows the Waskatenau Bridge, one of the multi-span two-girder line bridges on which repairs and retrofit were carried out.

A typical CIF susceptible detail is at intersections of longitudinal and transverse welds, which often occurs at intersections of transverse and longitudinal stiffeners or of transverse stiffeners and gusset plate (*Fig. 9a*). The horizontal gusset plate welds intersect with the vertical transverse stiffener welds, hence, creating all three conditions required for CIF. If there was a gap between the welds (minimum 6 mm (3)), there would be sufficient ductility in the girder web for brittle fracture to be avoided. *Fig. 9b* shows a retrofit for this detail which consists of milling a 75 mm diameter hole through the web at the intersection and completely removing the stiffener to web welds. This method requires locating the intersection point on the other side of the web. Note that the retrofit requires that all edges around the retrofit hole be ground smooth not to create any stress raisers which could lead to cracking in the member.

Fatigue cracks are more likely to occur in details with lower allowable stress ranges (Category E or E1 details in Canadian standards (2) and details with low detail category numbers in the Eurocode). In highway bridges, live loads from traffic, mainly heavy trucks, typically dominate for fatigue. Low fatigue category details include terminations of longitudinal welds in tension or stress reversal zones.

Fig. 9: CIF Susceptible Detail at Intersection of Gusset Plates and Transverse Stiffener: a) Pre-Retrofit Condition, b) Retrofitted Detail (Adapted from 5)

Fig. 10a shows the termination of a welded longitudinal stiffener in a stress reversal zone of a welded steel girder. The detail is a Category E detail in Canadian Standards or a Category 56 detail in accordance with the Eurocode (6). When terminated in stress-reversal zones, analysis of these bridges demonstrated that allowable stress ranges were exceeded, hence, there was high potential for fatigue cracking to occur over time. This detail can be retrofitted by coring a relief hole at the stiffener end. Ideally, the relief hole is placed so that the weld and stiffener ends are removed to catch and arrest any fatigue cracks which may have formed.

Some of the bridges also have stiffener connection plates between the transverse stiffener and the girder web. *Fig. 10b* shows such a plate at a top flange to diaphragm stiffener connection. These plates were installed during girder fabrication to avoid transverse stiffener to flange welds. It has been shown since that the longitudinal stiffener connection plate to flange weld has a lower fatigue category than welding the transverse stiffener directly to the flange. The allowable fatigue stress ranges for this unfavourable fatigue detail are typically exceeded in flexural tension zones of the girder. In addition, the detail shown in *Fig. 10b* is subjected to distortional fatigue from out-of-plane load effects imposed from the diaphragm attached to the transverse stiffener, which adds to the stress state in the member. This detail was repaired by carefully removing the cracked weld, verifying that the flange is uncracked, and then placing a new weld. Smoothing the weld minimized the risk for stress raisers.

Fig. 10: a) Relief Hole at Longitudinal Stiffener End, b) Rewelding of Cracked Weld, and c) Ultrasonic Peening of Weld Toes and Terminations (Adapted from and 5 and 7)

On the Waskatenau Bridge, a trial program was carried out with ultrasonic peening (8) in an attempt to improve the fatigue life of low category fatigue details and reducing the need for regular inspections and repairs in the future. Peening is a method of cold working the material surface to produce an outer layer of compressive residual stresses balanced by residual tensile stresses below the surface. The compressive stresses in the surface layer significantly delay or prevent the formation of surface cracks. Laboratory tests on peened welded details showed that peening was sometimes so effective that the fatigue crack initiation occurred away from the fatigue critical detail (9). Fig. 10c shows an ultrasonic peening treatment at a gusset plate to flange welded detail: both weld toes and the weld terminations were treated, since these are the areas where the risk of fatigue crack initiation is the highest. The ultrasonic peening treatment proved to be easy to perform in a field application thanks to the portability of the equipment.

The repairs and retrofit of fatigue and fracture-prone details decreases structural risk and increases the service life. Ideally, the retrofit and repairs enhance the structure, as was the case with the removal of CIF susceptible details, coring of fatigue relief holes or ultrasonic peening. All repairs were easy to carry out without the need of heavy equipment. More details on CIF and fatigue retrofit on Alberta bridges can be found in (7).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Many Canadian highway steel bridges are now over 50 years old and require renewal to extend their service life. Renewal strategies need to be carefully crafted for each requirement to determine the most efficient and appropriate way. The case studies demonstrated approaches to three different renewal demands: Case study I demonstrated an efficient strengthening scheme which allowed for enhancement of the structure's functionality and roadside safety through deck widening and barrier replacement. Case study II showed the importance of the maintenance of coating systems and how cross-section loss due to corrosion can be addressed efficiently. Case study III demonstrated how fatigue and fracture-prone details, often occurring bridges which were built prior to modern fatigue and fracture detailing, can be retrofitted and improved. All case studies demonstrate how structures can be renewed instead of being replaced, which is an important sustainability consideration.

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